

The formation and distribution of exhaust gases from vehicles on city street roads.

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Abstract: This article provides information on the formation and distribution of exhaust gases from vehicles on city street roads, as well as their solutions.

Keywords: Motor transport, traffic flow, economy, exhaust gases.

Introduction: Today, reducing the problem of exhaust gases coming out of motor vehicles in cities is a very urgent problem in urban planning and is increasing from year to year. A sharp increase in exhaust gases, along with a negative impact on the work activity, rest of people, causes several diseases. The fight against exhaust gases in our country is one of the most important issues of urban planning. The choice of noise reduction methods is made through the developed noise map in the city area.

The rapid growth of motor vehicles in urban areas in images causes sharply negative consequences for their environment. In Tashkent, the main source of atmospheric air pollution is harmful gases released from motor vehicles into the atmospheric air. This situation is the reason for causing great environmental problems in urban planning. The increasing number of vehicles is also causing a number of inconveniences, not only causing a lot of harm to the population and the environment. Taking the example of the city of Tashkent, the increasing traffic flow and the resulting traffic jams caused by the long traffic jams, the violation of the traffic schedule of vehicles, the situation of late stay of the population in service areas, as well as the increasing traffic accidents, have become an urgent problem of our city in recent years.

According to the Statistics Department of Tashkent City in 2018, a total of 210,000 tons of pollutants were released into the atmospheric air in Tashkent City in 2017, of which 3,750,663 industrial organizations and 140,8,000 tons were released into the atmospheric air by stationary and moving sources in the city.

Through the spread of a large amount of harmful gases and fumes into the atmosphere, the human body is poisoned, nausea occurs with poor blood circulation. At the beginning of such diseases - pain in the head, damage to the central nervous system, as well as allergic

diseases occur. All these effects can cause an accident, reducing labor productivity (50-60%). Scientists have proven that infectious skin diseases, tuberculosis and wound diseases that occur in cities are directly caused by toxic gases and fumes [1].

To date, the types of fuel vehicles are increasing, but it is advisable to use the most economical, safe and especially less harmful to ecology from the inside of these fuels. Currently, fuel that is cheaper than diesel fuel is considered popular, as well as methane gas, which releases less toxic substances into ecology. Our country is a gas producing and exporting country. In recent years, methane gas fuel stations have been widely introduced throughout the Republic.

Methods. Enterprises engaged in the activities of the transfer of cars to gas fuel in Tashkent City according to the information of the IIB of Tashkent City, by the end of 2017, 1658 (plan 1400) vehicles were transferred from gasoline to gas (methane) fuel, as a result of which the amount of gas thrown into atmospheric air was reduced to 759.8 tons [2-3].

Today, the number of cars around the world is 800 million. In excess of the grain, 85% of these are passenger cars, and 15% are freight cars. Cars are considered the most active oxygen-absorbing.

In order for a modern car to burn 1 kg of gasoline, 12m³ pollutes the air or consumes 250 l of oxygen in the oxygen compartment.

If we compare this value with human, a person gains 20 kg (15.5m³) per day and 7.5 t of air during the year. 1 hectare of forest produces 3t of oxygen in a year.

Results and Discussion: The results of the studies show that the concentration of toxic gases released from road transport the maximum value is mainly collected in a person's height, which further increases the effect of toxic gases on the human body.

Pollution of the atmosphere has a negative impact on the health of the axoli, the condition and originality of plants, buildings, metal structures, historical monuments, etc.

The decrease in the amount of emissions into the atmosphere is directly related to the decrease in the capacity of industrial enterprises and the fall in the volume of cargo

transportation in transport. The amount of emissions into the atmosphere of axoli per capita decreased to 183.7 kg dap in 2002 and 90.1 kg in 2012.

More than 51% dap of harmful compounds polluting the atmosphere comes to carbon monoxide (is gas-SO), sulfur dioxide -16%, hydrocarbons -17.9%, nitrogen oxides -8.9%, solid compounds 6%, and other harmful emissions -0.2% (2016) (14kurgazma).

In the main industries in the Republic, the retention and neutralization of harmful compounds is not at the level of demand. Payments and fines are established for enterprises in case of contamination of the territory in excess of the specified amount.

To reduce atmospheric pollution in industry:

Launch of new cleaning devices and increase the efficiency introduction of low-waste and waste-free technologies; the exclusion of enterprises and the implementation of other activities is necessary. The main source of air pollution of the vehicle complex is considered to be about 70% of atmospheric pollution. The main polluting compounds are is gas, nitrogen oxides, hydrocarbons, benzapirene, aldehydes and lead. Transport directly pollutes the chayote moxite, causing humans to accumulate lead and other toxic and carcinogenic compounds.

The transition of Uzbekistan to a market economy and the implementation of various environmental measures in recent years is accompanied by a decrease in the amount of emissions into the atmosphere. If in 1990 year 4 million from sources moving to the atmosphere and stagnant. if more than a ton of harmful compounds were released, this figure amounted to 2 million in 1995 year. the decrease in the amount of emissions into the atmosphere, which has decreased to tons, is directly related to the decrease in the capacity of industrial enterprises and the fall in the volume of cargo transportation in transport.

Within the framework of the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on the protection of atmospheric air" adopted in 1996, the documents are defined as the main tasks of the laws on the protection of atmospheric air:

- maintaining the natural composition of atmospheric air;
- prevention and reduction of chemical, physico-biological and other effects harmful to atmospheric air;

- special regulation of the activities of state bodies, enterprises, institutions, organizations public associations and citizens in the sphere of protection of atmospheric air.

Conclusion: As a result of the studies carried out, we conclude that:

- Despite the increasing density of the street-road network in Tashkent City, the level of load on this street is extremely high (higher than 2500 Auto/hours on each side);
- Most of the 95% of moving vehicles are passenger cars;
- The level of exhaust gas circulating from the motor vehicle throughout the city of Tashkent is 140.8 thousand tons released into the atmospheric air by stasionar and moving sources in the city.
- Construction (red at the same time in this area) at the expense of the absence of street elements (except lotoc and trotuar) in the line range, that is, greening on this line, the construction of special blocking decorative structures, the possibility of designing the ground level with the commuting part at different levels is not available (or economically ineffective).

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